

FORTY-FIFTH ANNUAL SYMPOSIUM ON FREQUENCY CONTROL

ULTRA-LOW-NOISE 8.3 GHz DIELECTRIC RESONATOR OSCILLATOR

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ABSTRACT

A parallel feedback 8.3 GHz Dielectric Resonator Oscillator (DRO) is designed by evaluating the residual phase noise of the GaAs FET amplifier and the resonant structure (RS). The resonant structure consists of two-port, dielectric resonator coupled to 50 ohm microstrip lines housed inside a copper cavity. The absolute phase noise of the DRO was measured by using a Hewlett Packard (HP) 3047A phase noise measurement system. The oscillator exhibited a single sideband (SSB) phase noise of -67 dBc/Hz at 100 Hz offset frequency. The loaded Q of the RS was measured to be 15,000 at room temperature. The in-house fabricated specially-designed GaAs FET amplifier exhibited a SSB residual phase noise of -150 dBc/Hz at a 1 kHz carrier offset frequency. The loaded Q of the resonant structure and the residual noise of the GaAs FET amplifier was measured again at liquid nitrogen temperature (77K). The loaded Q of the RS at 77K more than doubled but the residual phase noise of the amplifier degraded by as much as 45 dBc/Hz at 10 Hz carrier offset frequency.

INTRODUCTION

The Dielectric Resonator Oscillator (DRO) operating at 8.3 GHz reported in this paper has been shown to have excellent phase noise and temperature stability. Systems operating at X through Ku band frequency ranges with stringent performance requirements can benefit from this specially designed, high-performance DRO. System designers now have the option of selecting fundamentally operated high frequency DROs (5-10 GHz) without sacrificing the critical performance. DROs will play very important roles in future military and commercial system because of their simple construction, small size, high efficiency, low cost, spurious-free RF output spectrum, and good reliability.

OSCILLATOR DESIGN, CONSTRUCTION AND PERFORMANCE

A sinusoidal oscillator circuit can be classified as a two-port active device with a two-port passive network in a feedback configuration or a one-port active device in parallel with a one-port passive network. In order to sustain sinusoidal oscillations, the system transfer function must contain a pair of poles located slightly in the right-half complex plane. When dc power is applied, the noise will give rise to a growing sinusoidal output voltage which will eventually be limited by the circuit's nonlinearities. When the poles are relatively close to the complex axis, the nonlinearities observed will be small. When the poles are placed far into the right-half plane, the nonlinearities observed will be quite large due to large loop gain.

Figure 1 shows a block diagram of a transmission-mode dielectric resonator stabilized feedback-loop oscillator design. The analysis of basic feedback type of circuitry was first given by Leeson [1]. The feedback-loop oscillator configuration allows the circuit designer to isolate faulty components by measuring the residual phase noise of the components before the components are employed in the oscillator circuit. The flicker of frequency noise (30dB/decade) originating as a result of flicker of phase noise in the oscillator resonator and/or amplifier can be estimated using the formula given in ref. [2]. Because of the above circuit advantage, we have chosen the feedback DRO as our approach for fabricating X-band frequency sources. The top view of a two-port resonant structure is shown in Figure 2. The two-port resonant structure and the amplification stages are described in the following paragraph.

The resonant structure shown in Figure 2 consists of a zero ppm/°C dielectric resonator (DR) procured from Murata Erie, Inc. The resonator is housed inside a critically dimensioned

copper cavity. Coupling is achieved via 50 ohm microstrip transmission lines. The puck (DR) position and the microstrip line separation inside the cavity was optimized to give the highest loaded Q and minimum insertion loss. The resonant structure has a loaded Q of 15,000 with 13 dB of insertion loss at room temperature. Figure 3 shows the loaded Q measurement data. A mechanical tuning screw was built into the cavity to provide tuning capability. The input and the output 50 ohm microstrip line was constructed on 0.25 mm (10 mil) thick RT/duroid board. The board is soldered to the bottom of the cavity. Residual phase noise measurement was performed on the resonant structure to see the presence of 1/f noise. The test set up for the noise measurement is shown in Figure 4. As shown in Figure 4, an ETDL DRO was used as the frequency source to obtain a decent system floor. The system floor and the residual phase noise of the resonant structure are shown in Figure 5 and 6, respectively.

Two amplifiers were needed to overcome the insertion loss of the dielectric resonator and to provide excess loop gain in the feedback dielectric resonator oscillator. At first a single stage amplifier was designed using a Fujitsu FSX52WF GaAs FET. The input and the output matching network, stability, and the gain performance were analyzed using super compact CAD software. The amplifier circuit was constructed on 0.25 mm (10 mil) RT/duroid 5880 board. The amplifier was biased at 8 volt with 100 mA of drain current. The amplifier was stable and has a gain of 10 dB at 8.3 GHz. The input and the output VSWR was better than 2:1. The residual phase noise of the single stage GaAs FET amplifier was measured using a HP 3047A phase noise measurement system. The measurement test setup is shown in figure 4. The amplifier exhibited a SSB residual phase noise of better than -150 dBc/Hz at a 1 kHz carrier offset frequency. The measured phase noise plot is shown in Figure 7. After characterizing the amplifier and the resonant structure the complete oscillator was fabricated on RT/duroid 5880 board. Phase trimming was necessary to start the oscillator.

Due to lack of a second source with VCO capability, the absolute phase noise of the 8.3 GHz DRO was measured by down converting the test DRO to 95 MHz. The down conversion was achieved by mixing the 8.3 GHz DRO with a High-overtone Bulk Acoustic Resonator (HBAR) oscillator. Then the measurement was made by phase locking the 95 MHz down-

converted signal to an HP 8662A frequency synthesizer driven from an external 10 MHz VCXO. The absolute phase noise measurement test set up is shown in Figure 8. The DRO exhibited a SSB phase noise of -67 dBc/Hz at a 100 Hz carrier offset frequency. The phase noise plot is shown in Figure 9. The measured data are 6-8 dBc/Hz better than any other published data.

Frequency stability and RF output power vs temperature were measured by using a computer-controlled temperature chamber. The total frequency shift from -50°C to +20°C is only 25 ppm and from -50°C to +50°C is 65 ppm. The frequency vs temperature plot is shown in Figure 10. The frequency vs temperature stability of our free-running DRO is about five times better than available production DRO. RF output power variation over the temperature range is shown in Figure 11. Typical RF output power at room temperature is +15dBm.

DIELECTRIC RESONATOR AT 77K

Behavior of the resonant structure described in figure 2 was investigated at liquid nitrogen temperature. The loaded Q of the resonant structure at 77K was measured to be about 33,000 which is about 2.5 times better than the room temperature data. The insertion loss of the resonator improved from 13 dB at room temperature to 9.5 dB at 77K. Figure 12 shows the loaded Q measurement data at 77K. The total resonant frequency drift from room temperature to 77K was less than 400 kHz.

GaAs FET AND BJT AMPLIFIERS AT 77K

An attempt was made to measure the absolute phase noise of a 9 GHz DRO at liquid nitrogen temperature. The 9 GHz DRO was built to solve frequency stability problem of a miniature beacon transponder. We were expecting to see 6-8 dBc/Hz improvement in the absolute phase noise at 77K due to loaded Q enhancement of the resonator, but instead we saw spectral degradation during the noise measurement. At this point a decision was made to measure the residual phase noise of the GaAs FET amplifier at 77K to try to determine the source of the degradation. The amplifier was constructed on RT/duroid board using a commercially available hermetic metal/ceramic package unmatched GaAs FET. The amplifier circuit was exposed to the environment during measurement. During room temperature measurement, the amplifier was placed inside a RF shielded oven and during

liquid nitrogen temperature measurement the amplifier was placed inside a RF shielded cryogenic chamber. The system floor, the residual phase noise of the amplifier at room temperature and at 77K are shown in Figure 13, Figure 14 and Figure 15, respectively. The amplifier was biased at 8VDC with 200 mA of drain current. The amplifier was completely immersed in liquid nitrogen and bubbling was observed during measurement. No attempt is being made at this time to explain why the amplifier performance degraded at 77K.

Similar measurements were performed on a MMIC 2-stage 8.6 GHz GaAs FET amplifier, a 8.3 GHz GaAs FET amplifier and a 8.9 GHz internally matched power GaAs FET amplifier. In these measurements the unpackaged amplifier was surrounded by liquid nitrogen without being immersed in it. This arrangement was necessary to avoid bubbling during measurement. Figure 16 and Figure 17 show the residual phase noise of the MMIC amplifier at room temperature and at 77K respectively. Figure 18 shows the residual phase noise of a 8.3 GHz amplifier at 77K. Room temperature data for this amplifier is shown in Figure 7. Figure 19 and Figure 20 show the phase noise of internally matched amplifier at room temperature and at 77K respectively. In each case the residual noise of the amplifiers degraded between 10Hz and 100 Hz offset frequencies.

A 2 GHz BJT amplifier was also designed and tested at 77K. This amplifier circuit was constructed on duroid board which was also exposed to the environment during measurement. The gain of the BJT amplifier dropped from 15 dB at room temperature to 8 dB at 77K. The amplifier was completely immersed in the liquid nitrogen during measurement. Figure 21 shows the system floor at 2 GHz. Figure 22 and Figure 23 show the amplifier residual phase noise at room temperature and at 77K respectively. The 1/f noise of the BJT amplifier at room temperature is masked by the system noise as indicated by the measured system noise floor. The phase noise of BJT amplifier at 77K degraded between 10 Hz and 1 kHz carrier offset frequencies with nominal bias condition. However, the phase noise performance of the amplifier at 77K improved as the bias condition was increased. The result is shown in figure 24.

CONCLUSIONS

The free-running 8.3 GHz DRO reported here exhibits state-of-the-art

phase noise and frequency stability. The oscillator is small in size, 2.54 cm x 2.54 cm x 2.54 cm (1 cubic inch) and offers a spurious-free output spectrum. The basic design of the oscillator is of simple construction and employs low cost commercially available electronic components.

The loaded Q enhancement of the dielectric resonator and the noise degradation of unpackaged GaAs FET and BJT amplifiers at 77K has been reported. Investigations are underway to explain the phase noise degradation of GaAs FET amplifier at 77K.

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REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1. FEEDBACK DRO BLOCK DIAGRAM.

1 Metal Cylinder
2 50-ohm Microstrip Line
3 Dielectric Resonator
4 Low-loss, Dielectric Spacer

FIGURE 2. TOP VIEW OF TWO-PORT RESONANT STRUCTURE.

FIGURE 3. LOADED Q MEASUREMENT AT ROOM TEMPERATURE.

FIGURE 4. AMPLIFIER/RESONANT STRUCTURE RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE MEASUREMENT TEST SET-UP WITH SINGLE-SIDED SPURIOUS CALIBRATION.

FIGURE 5. SYSTEM FLOOR AT 8.3 GHz USING ETDL DRO AS FREQUENCY SOURCE.

FIGURE 6. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF RESONANT STRUCTURE.

FIGURE 7. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF SINGLE-STAGE 8.3 GHz GaAs FET AMPLIFIER AT ROOM TEMPERATURE.

FIGURE 8. 8.3 GHz DRO PHASE NOISE MEASUREMENT TEST SETUP.

FIGURE 9. ABSOLUTE PHASE NOISE OF 8.3 GHz DRO.

FIGURE 10. FREQUENCY vs TEMPERATURE PLOT.

FIGURE 11. RF OUTPUT POWER vs TEMPERATURE.

FIGURE 12. LOADED Q AT 77K.

FIGURE 13. SYSTEM FLOOR AT 9 GHz.

FIGURE 14. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF 9 GHz GaAs FET AMPLIFIER AT ROOM TEMPERATURE.

FIGURE 15. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF 9 GHz GaAs FET AMPLIFIER AT 77K.

FIGURE 16. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF 8.6 GHz MMIC 2-STAGE GaAs FET AMPLIFIER AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

FIGURE 17. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF 8.6 GHz MMIC 2-STAGE GaAs FET AMPLIFIER AROUND 77K.

FIGURE 18. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF 8.3 GHz GaAs FET AMPLIFIER AROUND 77K.

FIGURE 19. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF INTERNALLY MATCHED GaAs FET AMPLIFIER AT ROOM TEMPERATURE.

FIGURE 20. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF INTERNALLY MATCHED GaAs FET AMPLIFIER AROUND 77K.

FIGURE 21. SYSTEM FLOOR AT 2 GHz.

FIGURE 22. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF 2 GHz BJT AMPLIFIER AT ROOM TEMPERATURE.

FIGURE 23. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF 2 GHz BJT AMPLIFIER AT 77K.

FIGURE 24. RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE OF 2 GHz BJT AMPLIFIER AT 77K WITH INCREASED BIAS CONDITION.